

SUSCEPTIBILITY OF *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* AND *Staphylococcus aureus* FROM WOUND INFECTIONS TO GEL AND ETHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACTS OF ALOE VERA (*Aloe vera linne*).

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ABSTRACT

Studies was carried out to determine the susceptibility of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* from wound infections to the gel and ethanolic leaf extracts of Aloe vera plants. The bacteria associated with the wound infections in this study, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, were isolated and identified by standard microbiological and biochemical methods. Susceptibility test revealed that *Staphylococcus aureus* was susceptible to both Aloe vera gel and the ethanolic leaf extracts with zones of inhibition of 18.0mm and 4.0mm respectively. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was susceptible to Aloe vera ethanolic leaf extracts only with a zone of inhibition of 4.0mm but resistant to Aloe vera gel.

Keywords: Susceptibility, Aloe Vera, Wound, Inhibition, Extract.

INTRODUCTION

A wound is a break in the continuity of the skin. They range from small laceration to severe wide-spread injuries (Roper, 2002).

There are various descriptions of wounds which include: traumatic wounds, arterial ulcers, venous ulcers, diabetic foot ulcers, pressure ulcers and burn wounds. Studies by Spicer (2002) showed that most wounds result from common accidents such as falls, mishandling of sharp objects, accidents with tools or machinery or vehicular accidents. They could be classified as open or closed wounds. In relation to the presence of bacteria in the wounds, wounds have been grouped into: sterile, contaminated, colonized and infected wounds. (Dossey *et al*, 1992).

Infection of wounds may occur from a variety of sources such as the patient's own normal flora, the medical personnel in charge of the patient, the immediate environment, or the hospital equipments (Hudak *et al*, 1990).

Bacteria are the basic cause of wound infections. A wound infection is the successful invasion, establishment and growth of microorganisms in the tissues of an injured host which may be acute or chronic (Madigan *et al*, 2000). Certain bacterial species occur frequently in all forms of wound infections which may have occurred as a result of the skin normal flora becoming opportunistic pathogens. These infecting bacteria include: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, Diphtheroids sp, *E. coli*, Klebsiella sp, some anaerobic gram negative rods like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and some fungi species (Spicer, 2002).

Aloe vera Linne or Aloe barbadensis Miller is a succulent form of the Aloe family of which there are about 400 different species. They originate from the African continent. The plant is made up of thick leaves which contain its water supply to survive long periods of drought. (Foster, 1999). If the green skin of the leaf is removed, a clear mucilaginous substance called the gel appears. It contains the fibers, water and the ingredients to retain the water in the leaf.

The gel stimulates cell growth and as such enhances the restoration of damaged skin. Aloe gel is perhaps the most widely recognized herbal medicine in the United States today; it is used to relieve thermal burn, sun burn and promotes wound healing (Foster, 1999).

Research suggests that Aloe gel can help stimulate body immune system (Davis, 1997). Although a lot of works have been carried out on the medical use of Aloe vera gel, there is still little information on the uses of the leaf extracts which has informed the basis for this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

A total of 60 wound samples were collected from patients on admission in Lagos University Teaching Hospital, Lagos State, Nigeria based on the age, and sex of the patients and types of the wound involved. Samples were collected by swabbing the surface of the wound with sterile swab sticks. Pus were collected into sterile universal bottles. The swab sticks were put back into the swab containers and properly labeled before taking them to the laboratory for analysis.

Culturing and Identification of Organisms

The collected samples on the swab sticks were inoculated into nutrient broth in sterile universal bottles and labeled accordingly before incubating at 37°C for 24h. Making use of sterile wire-loops, small sample from each bottle was subcultured into corresponding MacConkey agar and blood agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24h. Blood agar plates were incubated anaerobically in a candle extinction jar at 37°C for 24h. Following incubation, the colonies were observed closely for their growth characteristics on the agar plates and identified based on their cultural, morphological and biochemical characteristics according to the schemes of Burchaman and Gibbons (1974), Cowan and Steel (1974) and Macfaddin (1980).

Pure colonies of the bacterial isolates were inoculated into agar slants, incubated at 37°C for 24h after which they were stored in the refrigerator until needed for further studies.

Preparation of Aloe Vera Gel and Ethanolic Leaf Extracts

Aloe vera leaves were obtained from the Botanical garden, University of Lagos, Akoka, Lagos and washed thoroughly with distilled water. The gel was extracted into a sterile 100ml beaker by carefully peeling off the skin of the leaf and applying a gentle squeeze. The collected gel were covered and immediately kept in the refrigerator until ready for use.

The leaves from which the gels have been drained were air-dried, ground and soaked in 90% ethanol for 4 days. This was later filtered and the filtrates evaporated to dryness using a rotary evaporator. The extracts were dissolved in sterile water, and used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

Different Petri dishes containing sterile nutrient agar were inoculated with 0.1ml of *staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, mixed thoroughly by gently swirling and left undisturbed on the table for about 1h.

Ten millimeter diameter wells were bored on the surface of each agar plate for the aloe vera gel and the ethanolic leaf extracts using a sterile cork-borer after which 0.1ml each of the gel and ethanolic leaf extracts was delivered into separate wells in each plate. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24h. Each plate was observed and the diameter of zones of inhibition activity of each extract were measured in milliliter using a transparent ruler.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the ages, sex and distribution of cases of wound infections and their percentage occurrence. From the samples collected, adults had occurrence frequency of 40 while children had occurrence frequency of 20.

The microorganisms isolated from the various wound infections, their biochemical reactions and zones of inhibition are shown in Table 2. The two microorganisms isolated from the various wounds are *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

The results of the antimicrobial activities of Aloe vera gel and the leaf extracts on the test organisms are shown in Table 3. Both Aloe vera gel and the leaf extracts were inhibitory to *Staphylococcus aureus* with

18.0mm and 4.0mm as zones of inhibition respectively, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is susceptible to Aloe vera ethanolic leaf extract only with a zone of inhibition of 4.0mm but resistant to Aloe vera gel.

Figure 1 illustrates a bar chart of the total frequency occurrence of the different types of wound specimens. From the findings, burnt thigh had the highest frequency of occurrence of 17 while surgical case had the lowest occurrence of 1.

Table 1: Sex and Age distribution of cases of Wound Infections and their Percentage Occurrence

Types of wound	Adult		Occurrence adult	% occurrence adult	Children		Occurrence children	% occurrence children	Total occurrence	% Total occurrence
	Male	Female			Male	Female				
Bullet injury	05	-	05	8.33	-	-	-	-	0.5	8.33
Burnt thigh	08	06	14	23.33	02	01	03	5.00	17	28.33
Sutured leg	-	-	-	-	04	01	05	8.33	05	8.33
Wound abscess	06	03	09	15.00	02	01	03	5.00	12	20.00
Wound on the knee	-	-	-	-	05	02	07	11.67	07	11.67
Burns on the ankle	04	-	04	6.67	-	-	-	-	04	6.67
Penetration wound by knife	04	-	04	6.67	-	-	-	-	04	6.67
Finger abscess	-	-	-	-	01	01	02	3.33	02	3.33
Amputated leg	02	01	03	5.00	-	-	-	-	03	5.00
Surgical case	-	01	01	1.67	-	-	-	-	01	1.67
Number of cases of wound infections	20	11	40	66.6	14	06	20	33.1	60	

Table 2: Isolates, Biochemical Reactions and Antibigram

Age	Sex	Types of wound specimen	Microscopy	Gram	Motility	Oxidase	Coagulase	Catalase	Identification	Zone of Inhibition	
										Aloe vera gel (25mg/ml)	Aloe leaf (25mg/ml)
AD	M	Bullet injury	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet injury	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet injury	4-5	+	-	-	+	-	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet injury	2-3						No significant growth		
AD	M	Bullet injury	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	4-5	-	+	+	-	-	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	R	3+

Table 2 cont.....

AD	M	Bullet thigh	1-2						No significant growth		
AD	M	Bullet thigh	6-7	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	8-9	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+
AD	F	Bullet thigh	3-4	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+
AD	F	Bullet thigh	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	1-2	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+
AD	F	Bullet thigh	4-5	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+
AD	F	Bullet thigh	5-6	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	4-5	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+
CH	M	Bullet thigh	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	F	Bullet thigh	2-3	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	4-5	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+
CH	F	Bullet thigh	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	1-2	+/-	+/-	+/-	+/-	+/-	<i>S. aureus</i> / <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	3+/R	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	0-1	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Bullet thigh	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	M	Sutured leg	3-4	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	F	Sutured leg	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	M	Sutured leg	4-5	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	M	Sutured leg	2-3	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	M	Sutured leg	6-9	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Wound abscess	4-5	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	F	Wound abscess	4-5	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	F	Wound abscess	3-4	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	M	Wound abscess	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	F	Wound abscess	2-3	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Wound abscess	4-5	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	F	Wound abscess	0-1	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	M	Wound abscess	4-5	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Wound abscess	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Wound abscess	0-1	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Wound abscess	2-3	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Wound abscess	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
CH	F	Wound on knee	2-3	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+

Table 2 cont.....

CH	M	Wound on knee	0-1									
CH	M	Wound on knee	4-5	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	2-3	-	+	+	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
CH	F	Wound on knee	0-1	+	+	-	-	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	5-6	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	4-5	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	2-3	+	-	-	+	+	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+	
CH	F	Wound on knee	0-1	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	5-6	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+	
CH	M	Wound on knee	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
AD	M	Burns on the ankle	4-5	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> / <i>S. aureus</i>	R/3+	3+	
AD	M	Burns on the ankle	2-3						No significant growth			
AD	M	Burns on the ankle	1-2	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+	
AD	M	Burns on the ankle	7-8	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
AD	M	Penetration wound by knife on the hand	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
AD	M	Penetration wound by knife on the back	4-5	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> / <i>S. aureus</i>	R/3+	3+	
AD	M	Penetration wound by knife on the hand	3-4	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
AD	M	Penetration wound by knife on the chest	0-1	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> / <i>S. aureus</i>	R/3+	3+	
CH	M	Finger abscess	1-2	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	
CH	F	Finger abscess	3-4	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+	

Table 2 cont.....

AD	F	Amputated leg	0-1	+	-	-	+	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	3+	3+
AD	M	Amputated leg	5-6	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	-/+	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> / <i>S. aureus</i>	R/3+	3+
AD	M	Amputated leg	7-8						No significant growth		
AD	F	Surgical case	2-3	-	+	+	-	-	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	R	3+

+ - Positive M Male
 - - Negative F Female
 AD - Adult 3+ Sensitive
 CH - Children R Resistant

Table 3: Antimicrobial activities of Aloe vera Gel and Leaf Extract (25mg/ml) on Test Organisms

Test Organisms	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	
	Aloe vera gel	Aloe vera leaf
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	18.0	4.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	0.0	4.0

Keys

- | | |
|-----------------------|--------------------------------|
| A - Bullet injury | F - Burns on the ankle |
| B - Burnt thigh | G - Penetration wound by knife |
| C - Sutured leg | H - Finger abscess |
| D - Wound abscess | I - Amputated leg |
| E - Wound on the knee | J - Surgical case |

Bar Chart of Total Frequency of Occurrence of the Different Types of Wound Specimens.

DISCUSSION

The result shows that 48 of the 60 samples for this study show rich growth for *Staphylococcus aureus* while 12 show growth for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Table 2). However, the high frequency of *S. aureus* in wounds is not surprising because it is a normal flora of the human skin (Madigan *et al*, 2002).

The results show that both the Aloe vera gel and the leaf extracts have inhibitory effects on *S. aureus* with zones of inhibition of 18.0mm and 4.0mm respectively. This efficacy could be responsible for their popular use for the relief of many types of gastrointestinal irritations since *Staphylococcus aureus* form part of the normal flora of the skin, upper respiratory tract, and intestinal tract. (Foster, 1999, Grindley and Reynolds, 1986, Cheesbrough, 1984). The gel is also said to promote healing due to the presence of some components such as anthraquinones and hormones which possess antimicrobial, antifungal and antiviral activities (Davis, 1997).

The ethanolic leaf extracts had inhibitory effects on *Pseudomina aeruginosa* while the gel had no effect (Table 2). *Pseudomonas* is known to cause skin infections especially in burn sites, wounds and pressure sores and ulcers. The inhibitory effects of the leaf extracts of Aloe vera on the growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* gives credence to its reputation as a healing plant for burns.

CONCLUSION

Aloe vera plants originated from Africa and they are essentially grown in many parts of our country and as ornamental plant in many homes. Their therapeutic potential is well documented.

It is suggested that more investigations be carried out on this plant in order to fully exploit the medical potential of this free wonderful gift of nature to mankind.

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